

Outlining an HPC Co-Scheduler

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I. INTRODUCTION

In traditional High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters, nodes are typically allocated exclusively to applications. Due to the fact that MPI processes execute identical code on different data sets, they often disrupt each other by competing for shared resources such as Last-Level Caches (LLCs), memory, and network bandwidth. To address this issue, node sharing has been proposed—an approach based on the principle that applications can coexist efficiently as long as they do not compete for the same resources simultaneously [1]. Therefore, HPC systems can improve throughput and reduce job turnaround times, particularly for workloads with complementary resource demands.

While researchers have proposed node-sharing concepts, co-scheduling remains largely unexplored. In co-scheduling, a job’s runtime can lengthen or shorten depending on the applications it is paired with throughout its execution. This dynamic introduces a new perspective to scheduling, an already NP-complete problem [2].

In the process of designing an HPC co-scheduler, we identified that the following optimization opportunities should be exploited:

- 1) the resource allocation schema, which determines whether a job runs in exclusive or shared resources,
- 2) the waiting queue ordering, which indicates which job to execute first,
- 3) and the job placement within the available resources.

By exploiting these elements, we perform a series of experiments to evaluate their impact and derive preliminary estimates of trade-offs and optimization strategies in co-scheduling.

Currently, we examine the dynamics of HPC co-scheduling from a statistical point of view. Our findings show that while random co-scheduling pairings perform adequately, their effectiveness depends greatly on the characteristics of the workload and system utilization during pairing. Therefore, our work highlights strong correlations between key metrics, such as job speedup and system utilization, with respect to the makespan speedup. Furthermore, our results indicate that performance can be improved through careful pair-matching of co-executed jobs, as poor pairings may lead to significant degradation [3]. Regardless, maximizing resource utilization remains critical. Finally, we identify an opportunity for improved performance by co-scheduling multiple jobs concurrently when system resources permit.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A Resource and Job Management System (RJMS) coordinates the allocation of CPUs, memory, and accelerators to ensure efficient and fair job execution. It integrates a job scheduler and a resource manager to make policy-driven, informed decisions. Examples of modern RJMS tools include Slurm, Flux, and OAR. Adapting RJMS to the scale and complexity of HPC systems is challenging, often requiring large-scale testing and privileged access. To overcome this, researchers turn to simulation tools to evaluate new scheduling algorithms and resource management techniques. Thus, concerning the co-scheduling experiments, our work leverages the Efficient Lightweight Scheduling Estimator (ELiSE)¹ [4], a scheduler prototyping tool that allows researchers to efficiently develop and test co-scheduling algorithms of static or dynamic workloads without the need for a complex setup.

Although target metrics vary, they typically balance system-side goals such as throughput and utilization with user-side metrics such as job waiting and turnaround times, which often present conflicting goals. However, accurately evaluating scheduling algorithms is not straightforward, especially when biases and limitations in common optimization metrics are found [5]. Key metrics include makespan speedup, measuring workload completion time reduction compared to a baseline scheduler, and mean slowdown, quantifying user expectations by comparing turnaround time (execution and waiting) to execution time. Utilization reflects resource efficiency, with higher values indicating better usage.

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND APPROACH

To advance co-scheduling in HPC, we address the following research questions to optimize performance, resource utilization, and fairness:

- How should a co-scheduler, that is aware of workload characteristics, decide between exclusive or node-sharing allocation? In the absence of such knowledge, is random co-scheduling effective?
- In which cases should node-sharing not be performed at all?
- How do key co-scheduling metrics (e.g., mean job speedup, makespan speedup, mean slowdown, utilization) correlate with each other?

¹<https://github.com/cslab-ntua/elise>

- How should jobs be placed to optimize the gain captured from pairings and maximize resource utilization?
- Does reordering the waiting queue enhance system throughput, and how does this impact user fairness?
- Is it pragmatic to use exhaustive algorithms for scheduling multiple jobs simultaneously to reduce makespan, and if so, at what scale is this approach feasible compared to scheduling jobs individually?

IV. CONTRIBUTIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

To evaluate the co-execution approach and to also feed input to ELiSE, we ran experiments using MPI kernels from the NAS Parallel Benchmarks (NPB) and SPEChpc 2021 suites on the GRNET/ARIS and CINECA/Marconi supercomputers. Each application was initially run in exclusive nodes, then co-scheduled in pairs, with each application restricted to half the cores of the CPU socket. Our results indicate that co-execution delivers a mean job speedup of 13% [6], where job speedup is defined as the ratio of runtime under the exclusive policy to runtime under the node-sharing policy. However, in co-scheduling scenarios, our recent simulations using ELiSE, indicate that each job contributes a specific weight within a workload, motivating the use of the Weighted Mean Job Speedup (WMJS) for more accurate evaluation. The WMJS is additionally designated by the set of applications present in the workload and the frequency with which each appears. Using these new insights, we are nearing an answer to our first question—determining when co-scheduling is advantageous under random pairings.

Additionally, our observations reveal strong correlations among key performance metrics. Specifically, makespan speedup is closely linked to both system utilization and throughput, highlighting utilization as a critical factor deserving primary focus. Furthermore, the joint consideration of utilization and Weighted Mean Job Speedup (WMJS) exhibits an even stronger correlation with makespan speedup, suggesting that schedulers should optimize both metrics concurrently. From a user perspective, metrics such as mean job speedup and the number of under-performing applications suggest a trade-off in co-scheduling: when a job benefits from speedup, its paired jobs often experience a performance decline.

To address the next stages of our work, we are actively developing and evaluating co-scheduling algorithms under the ELiSE framework. Since exhaustively solving the scheduling problem is computationally prohibitive, our approach centers on pragmatic, greedy, and opportunistic strategies. These approaches aim to assign jobs in a way that minimizes resource fragmentation while fostering performance-beneficial co-locations. Preliminary results show that reordering jobs in the waiting queue can lead to significant improvements in makespan, however, at a cost of user fairness.

Lastly, we are investigating bulk scheduling strategies that capitalize on scenarios where multiple jobs are eligible for scheduling simultaneously. By making coordinated decisions across such job sets, we aim to approximate the benefits

of exhaustive optimization, potentially achieving better overall system utilization and performance. However, this raises critical questions about the trade-off between the complexity of such algorithms and their practical viability. Whether the performance gains justify the increased algorithmic complexity and whether such approaches can be feasibly implemented within real-world RJMS remains an open question that we aim to address in our ongoing work.

V. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The next phase entails an outlined action plan aimed at achieving our objectives, with an emphasis on the following key steps.

- We aim to design a class of (co-)scheduling algorithms that adapt to varying levels of application-specific knowledge, ranging from empirically observed co-execution speedups to predictions generated by machine learning (ML) models [7].
- We aspire to propose practical scheduling solutions to integrate co-scheduling while maintaining the option to preserve typical HPC behavior, such as designating a dedicated co-scheduling queue alongside a standard queue.
- We seek to introduce a range of co-scheduling strategies that tilt the balance between makespan improvement and user fairness and align with HPC infrastructure policies and service-level agreements (SLAs).
- We strive to assess, develop, implement, and evaluate an illustrative set of co-schedulers on real HPC systems using production RJMS such as SLURM or OAR.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my gratitude to Tsoukleidis-Karydakias Athanasios, Karapanagiotis Efstratios (the lead developer of ELiSE), and Myrsini Kellari for their valuable insights, contributions, and continuous support throughout the development of this work.

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